

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PHAM****FIRST NAME: ANH****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: (Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What a research argument is not?

- Kind of argument the goal is to win.¹**
- Reasoning based on evidence.
- Raise objections.
- Like a conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues.

2. When not to cite?

- It is common knowledge.²**

¹ Turabian, Kate L., et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 57.

² Laurent, Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition*. Bangui: Euclid University., 2021, 37.

- When in doubt.
 - When not necessary.
 - Your previous papers.
3. Tick all interrelated concerns need to be addressed in a research proposal.
- The “like-to do-ability.”
 - The “should-do-ability.”**³
 - The “want-to do-ability.”**⁴
 - The “do-ability.”**⁵
4. Action research is not.
- Systematic approach.
 - Collaborative action.
 - Democratic orientation.
 - Work alone style.**⁶
5. What are the three stages to analysis in grounded theory research?
- Open coding.**⁷

³ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: Sage, 2019). 202.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 202.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 202.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 253.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 273.

Axial coding.⁸

Convenient coding

Selective coding.⁹

6. Please select all the correct answers that a well-planned and logical research proposal should indicate.

The research design is clearly explained, credible, and achievable.¹⁰

Offers good reasons why others should be interested in the research.¹¹

Shows the researcher are capable and willing to conduct the proposed research.¹²

Research questions that are tied to the purpose and when answered, will shed light on the problem.

7. Select one character that differentiate researchable question to a question.

The researcher's knowledge and skills, and the availability of time and resources.¹³

The researcher's wanting to do.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 273.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 273.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 202.

¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 202.

¹² Bloomberg and Volpe, 202.

¹³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 309-311.

The practical feasibility or do-ability.¹⁴

The research topic is interesting, and the researcher already has the answer.

8. Select all the correct answers. Paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but.

No citations needed.

The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author.¹⁵

The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used.¹⁶

The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote.¹⁷

9. Select two trustworthiness criteria in qualitative study.

Creditability.¹⁸

Reliability.

Transferability.¹⁹

External validity.

¹⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 309-311.

¹⁵ Laurent and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition*. Bangui: Euclid University, 36.

¹⁶ Laurent and Gulma, 36.

¹⁷ Laurent and Gulma, 36.

¹⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 473-474.

¹⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 473-474.

10. Like hypotheses that can never be proven to be true, validity can never be absolutely established. The critical questions are:

- How much validity evidence is enough?**²⁰
- Can the adequate validity criterion for measures used in exploratory research that are designed to guide future research be relatively lower?**²¹
- Should the validity criterion for research on “high-stakes” assessment of professional competency needs to be extensive?**²²
- None of the above.

²⁰ Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Florida State University, 2017). 47.

²¹ Sampson, 47.

²² Sampson, 47.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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